

1 **REVIEW**

2 **Knock down to level up: Reframing RNAi for invertebrate ecophysiology**

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12 **Abstract**

13 Comparative ecophysiologicalists strive to understand physiological problems in non-model
14 organisms, but the use of molecular tools that manipulate gene expression such as RNA
15 interference (RNAi) are under-used in our field. Here, we provide a framework for invertebrate
16 ecophysiologicalists to use RNAi to answer questions focused on physiological processes, rather
17 than as a tool to investigate gene function. We specifically focus on non-model invertebrates, in
18 which the use of other genetic tools (*e.g.*, genetic knockout lines) are less likely. We argue that
19 because RNAi elicits a temporary manipulation of gene expression, and resources to carry out
20 RNAi are technically and financially accessible, it is an effective tool for invertebrate
21 ecophysiologicalists. We cover the terminology and basic mechanisms of RNA interference as an
22 accessible introduction for “non-molecular” physiologists, include a suggested workflow for
23 identifying RNAi gene targets and validating biologically relevant gene knockdowns, and
24 present a hypothesis-testing framework for using RNAi to answer common questions in the
25 realm of invertebrate ecophysiology. This review encourages invertebrate ecophysiologicalists to
26 use these tools and workflows to explore physiological processes and bridge genotypes to
27 phenotypes in their animal(s) of interest.

28
29 **Key words:** functional genomics, gene manipulation, genotype to phenotype, invertebrate
30 physiology, stress physiology

31

32 **Highlights**

- 33 • RNAi is an accessible genetic tool that is underused in invertebrate physiology
- 34 • The RNAi target should be chosen to disrupt a physiological process of interest
- 35 • To appropriately interpret RNAi experiments, validation of the RNAi is required
- 36 • Careful timing of RNAi can provide strong insight into physiological processes

37

PRE-PRINT

38 **List of Abbreviations**

39 bp: base pairs

40 Cas: CRISPR-associated

41 CRISPR: clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats

42 dsRNA: double-stranded RNA

43 miRNA: microRNA

44 mRNA: messenger RNA

45 RdRp: RNA-dependent RNA polymerase

46 RISC: RNA-induced silencing complex

47 RNAi: RNA interference

48 RNA-seq: RNA sequencing

49 RT-qPCR: real time quantitative PCR (polymerase chain reaction)

50 shRNA: short hairpin RNA

51 siRNA: short interfering RNA

52 SID: systemic RNAi-dependent

53 TALEN: transcription activator-like effector nuclease

54

55 **1 Introduction**

56 Understanding the relationship between environment and physiology at multiple levels of
57 biological organization is a core theme in comparative ecophysiology. While we have learned
58 much from laboratory model organisms about the relationships between genes and their function
59 at the cellular to whole organism level, model organisms hardly encapsulate the diversity of
60 organisms of interest to ecophysiologicalists (Matthews and Vosshall, 2020). For example, those
61 interested in stress tolerance physiology are more likely to make progress by studying organisms
62 with high tolerance for extreme environments rather than the relatively stress-intolerant model
63 organisms of fruit flies (*Drosophila melanogaster*) or mice (*Mus musculus*). Invertebrates
64 represent the vast majority of animal diversity and abundance (Bar-On et al., 2018; Mora et al.,
65 2011), providing ample research opportunities (with relatively little paperwork) for comparative
66 ecophysiologicalists. In addition, with the continued rapid development of genetic and molecular
67 biology techniques, it is increasingly feasible to generate hypotheses about the genetic
68 underpinnings of physiological traits in non-model organisms (*e.g.*, using ‘omics; Torson et al.,
69 2020), and then test those hypotheses using genetic manipulations (Dickinson et al., 2020;
70 Knight, 2020). However, it is a daunting task for most physiologists to fully develop a new
71 genetic model organism, complete with a sequenced genome and mutant lines (*cf.* Matthews and
72 Vosshall, 2020). In this review, we focus on **RNAi** (RNA interference), a method of temporary
73 genetic knockdown that can be used to study the ecophysiology of non-model invertebrate
74 animals.

75

76 Our main call to action is to refocus how we (comparative ecophysiologicalists) use RNAi. Rather
77 than using the technique to test the function of genes (gene-focused approach, *e.g.*, Toxopeus et

78 al., 2014), we want to use RNAi as a tool to manipulate processes (process-focused approach,
79 *e.g.*, Lebenzon et al., 2022) so we can better understand physiology at multiple levels of
80 biological organization (see *Section 5.1*). We can think of at least two complementary types of
81 questions that might be of interest to ecophysiologicalists and amenable to RNAi (Figure 1).
82 1) “Which (physiological) processes underlie a phenotype of interest?” This question is
83 particularly important to study in non-model organisms to better understand phenotypes that are
84 rare or not observed in traditional model organisms, for example the ability to migrate long
85 distances, enter dormant states like hibernation or diapause, or survive freezing. Many of these
86 rare (non-model) phenotypes can vary seasonally and with exposure to changing environmental
87 conditions, and thus we also ask, 2) “How does an animal’s environment influence those
88 physiological processes?” This allows physiologists to then explore how environmental
89 conditions (and challenges) regulate, disrupt, or otherwise affect organismal-level phenotypes.
90 When exploring Question 2, physiologists may reveal novel processes (or modulation of known
91 processes in a novel context), which can then be further explored via Question 1 (Figure 1).
92 While these questions are not novel, we have not seen many studies exploiting RNAi to answer
93 them. One of our goals is to provide concrete recommendations on how to use RNAi to answer
94 these types of questions (see *Section 5.5*), and help researchers make stronger connections
95 between **genotype** and **phenotype** in a physiological context.
96
97 We focus on RNAi because (as described in *Section 5.1*) this technique allows researchers to
98 manipulate gene expression at specific times and often in a temporary or partial way, providing
99 opportunities to study time- and environmentally sensitive physiological processes. RNAi also
100 works in a broad range of invertebrate taxonomic groups (Table 1). The critique of various

101 genetic manipulation methods such as RNAi, **morpholinos**, and **CRISPR** is covered elsewhere
102 for vertebrate animals (Kok et al., 2015; Zimmer et al., 2019), model invertebrates (Yamamoto-
103 Hino and Goto, 2013), plants and fungi (Agrawal et al., 2003; Svoboda, 2020), and cell lines
104 (Boettcher and McManus, 2015). The use of these genetic techniques is also well-summarized
105 for invertebrates in fields with a different focus from physiology, including developmental
106 biology (*e.g.*, sea urchins; Cui et al., 2017; Eisen and Smith, 2008) and pest control (*e.g.*, insects;
107 Scott et al., 2013; Zhu and Palli, 2020). To show how RNAi can be effectively used to answer
108 Questions 1 and 2 (Figure 1) in non-model invertebrates, we will briefly cover some terminology
109 (knockdowns and knockouts; *Section 2*) and the general mechanisms of RNAi (*Section 3*),
110 discuss the conditions under which RNAi is the most effective genetic manipulation tool (*Section*
111 *4*), and provide some practical guidance on designing and troubleshooting effective RNAi
112 experiments in a hypothesis-testing physiology context (*Section 5*).

113

114 **Figure 1. Bridging the gap between genotype and phenotype by using RNA interference to**
115 **manipulate physiological processes.** Rather than use RNAi to simply explore gene function, we
116 suggest using RNAi to manipulate downstream processes to better understand how underlying
117 mechanisms produce candidate organismal level phenotypes. Using questions 1 and 2,
118 physiologists can start to explore both the underlying mechanisms of physiological processes,
119 and how environments influence physiological processes, with both questions revealing novel
120 information to produce a feedback loop of physiological exploration.

121 **Table 1.** Select examples of species from major invertebrate phyla in which RNAi has been conducted.

Phylum	Class	Species	Reference
Porifera	Demospongiae	<i>Tethya wilhelma</i> , <i>Ephydatia muelleri</i> (sponges)	(Rivera et al., 2011)
Placozoa	Uniplacotomia	<i>Trichoplax adhaerens</i>	(Jakob et al., 2004)
Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	<i>Aiptasia pallida</i> (sea anemone)	(Dunn et al., 2007)
Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> (hydra)	(Ambrosone et al., 2012)
Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	<i>Cladonema pacificum</i> (jellyfish)	(Masuda-Ozawa et al., 2022)
Cnidaria	Octocorallia	<i>Acropora tenuis</i> (coral)	(Yuyama et al., 2021)
Echinodermata	Echinoidea	<i>Strongylocentrotus intermedius</i> (sea urchin)	(Han et al., 2021)
Echinodermata	Holothuroidea	<i>Apostichopus japonicus</i> (sea cucumber)	(Tian et al., 2017)
Platyhelminthes	Trematoda	<i>Schistosoma mansoni</i> (blood fluke)	(Correnti et al., 2005)
Platyhelminthes	Turbellaria	<i>Macrostomum lignano</i> (free-living flatworm)	(Wudarski et al., 2019)
Rotifera	Bdelloidea	<i>Adineta vaga</i> (bdelloid rotifer)	(Gardner and Schurko, 2020)
Rotifera	Monogononta	<i>Brachionus manjavacas</i> (monogonont rotifer)	(Snell et al., 2011)
Annelida	Clitellata	<i>Eudrilus eugeniae</i> (nightcrawler earthworm)	(Paul et al., 2022)
Mollusca	Bivalvia	<i>Hyriopsis cumingii</i> (pearl mussel)	(Huang et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2018)
Mollusca	Gastropoda	<i>Biomphalaria glabrata</i> (snail)	(Jiang et al., 2006)
Nematoda	Chromadorea	<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> (free-living nematode)	(Fire et al., 1998)
Nematoda	Chromadorea	<i>Brugia malayi</i> (parasitic nematode)	(Landmann et al., 2012)
Arthropoda	Arachnida	<i>Amblyomma americanum</i> (lone star tick)	(Aljamali et al., 2003)
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	<i>Daphnia magna</i> (water flea)	(Kato et al., 2011)
Arthropoda	Copepoda	<i>Tigriopus californicus</i> (copepod)	(Barreto et al., 2015)
Arthropoda	Insecta	<i>Aedes aegypti</i> , <i>Armigeres subalbatus</i> (mosquitoes)	(Infanger et al., 2004)
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	<i>Eriocheir sinensis</i> (Chinese mitten crab)	(Ma et al., 2016)
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	<i>Litopenaeus vannamei</i> (whiteleg shrimp)	(Hou et al., 2014)

122

123 **2 Knockdown vs. knockout experiments**

124 There are multiple approaches to manipulating genes and their proteins to better understand
125 physiological processes, only some of which are feasible in non-model organisms. In model
126 organisms with appropriate genetic tools, **gain-of-function** experiments (also called forward
127 genetics) can be conducted, in which the impact of increased expression of a gene of interest is
128 studied in genetic **knock-ins** (Doudna and Charpentier, 2014). **Loss-of-function** experiments
129 (also called reverse genetics), in which researchers examine the impact of decreased expression
130 of a gene of interest, are more common in non-model invertebrates (*e.g.*, Zimmer et al., 2019). In
131 addition, for some well-studied proteins, there are other ways to inhibit the function of gene
132 products such as administration of **pharmacological inhibitors** (*e.g.*, ouabain inhibits Na⁺/K⁺
133 ATPase function; Andersen et al., 2022). In this section, we focus on the loss-of-function genetic
134 approaches, including genetic **knockouts** and **knockdowns**, which can allow the researcher to
135 determine the impact of genetic disruption on **downstream** physiological processes.

136
137 **Knocking out** a gene ensures the gene product (protein) is completely non-functional or never
138 expressed. Generating a genetic knockout usually involves permanent changes to an organism's
139 genomic (chromosomal) DNA, induced either by **untargeted mutagenesis**, traditional **targeted**
140 **transformation** methods, or more modern targeted techniques such as **TALEN** and
141 CRISPR/Cas system (Boettcher and McManus, 2015). In traditional genetic model organisms,
142 many knockout lines have been developed and are maintained by facilities, such as the
143 Bloomington Drosophila Stock Centre (Indiana, USA). However, for non-model organisms,
144 researchers must develop their own genetic knockout lines, a process that is possible with tools
145 like CRISPR, but can be a multi-year, resource-intensive process (Matthews and Vosshall,

146 2020). However, if genetic lines can be successfully established, they can be maintained and
147 used many times over a researcher's career (Matthews and Vosshall, 2020), providing an
148 advantage over genetic manipulations with more temporary effects.

149

150 **Knocking down** a gene reduces the amount of functional gene product, and is often reversible.
151 Genetic knockdown can be achieved using **transgenic** lines (for model organisms) as well tools
152 that temporarily disrupt gene expression such as RNAi and morpholinos. Morpholinos are
153 antisense oligonucleotides that prevent translation of **target** mRNA into proteins, reducing the
154 abundance of the target protein (Blum et al., 2015; Eisen and Smith, 2008). This knockdown
155 technique works well in embryos and has traditionally been used in developmental biology with
156 organisms like sea urchins, zebrafish (*Danio rerio*), and *Xenopus* frogs (Blum et al., 2015; Eisen
157 and Smith, 2008). However, delivery of morpholinos into adult tissues is more challenging
158 (Moulton and Jiang, 2009). RNAi knocks down genes by degrading target mRNA in a range of
159 organisms and developmental stages (Setten et al., 2019; Svoboda, 2020; Zimmer et al., 2019),
160 the mechanisms of which we describe in the next section. The same facilities that maintain
161 genetic knockout lines also often maintain RNAi knockdown lines, such as the Transgenic RNAi
162 Project (TRiP) lines in *D. melanogaster* (Perkins et al., 2015; Yamamoto-Hino and Goto, 2013).
163 In non-model organisms, researchers usually conduct their own RNAi, resulting in temporary
164 knockdown of the target gene (Scott et al., 2013).

165

166 **3 Mechanisms of RNAi**

167 Understanding the origins and mechanisms of the RNAi response is integral to designing useful
168 RNAi experiments and interpreting their results. Many reviews already exist that describe the

169 biochemistry and molecular biology of this response (*e.g.*, Wilson and Doudna, 2013). The
170 RNAi response is naturally occurring, very conserved among eukaryotic cells, and likely evolved
171 as a defense mechanism against viruses (Obbard et al., 2008). Because many viruses have
172 genetic material in the form of dsRNA, eukaryotic cells have evolved a system of protein
173 complexes that can identify, bind to, and degrade single-stranded RNA (*e.g.*, mRNA)
174 complementary to this **exogenous** dsRNA, thereby preventing viral protein synthesis (Obbard et
175 al., 2008). The same pathways used to degrade RNA of viral origin can be used for regulation of
176 gene expression; for example **endogenous** small non-coding RNAs (*e.g.*, microRNAs and Piwi-
177 interacting RNAs) can bind to and target mRNA transcripts for breakdown (Pu et al., 2019).
178 Here will briefly summarize how exogenous dsRNA (generated by a researcher) is taken up by
179 cells and processed by RNAi machinery, leading to the (potentially systemic) knock down of
180 target mRNA (Figure 2).

181

183

184 **Figure 2. Schematic of the cellular RNAi response elicited when exogenous dsRNA is**
 185 **introduced into an organism.** To knock down gene expression, exogenous dsRNA must enter
 186 cells, where it is processed by RNAi core machinery to degrade complementary endogenous
 187 mRNA transcripts, which may systemically spread between cells and tissues. Numbers in the
 188 black boxes refer to sections in the text that explain the indicated mechanism.
 189

190 3.1 dsRNA uptake into cells

191 For effective RNAi, long (200 - 500 bp; Yu et al., 2013) dsRNA must be recognized and
 192 transported into cells, which can occur via multiple possible mechanisms (Figure 2). In an
 193 experimental setting, exogenous dsRNA targeting an mRNA transcript of interest can be
 194 synthesized *in vitro* and then introduced into an organism via injection, feeding, or (in some
 195 aquatic organisms) soaking/bathing in solution containing dsRNA (Dias et al., 2019; Lopez-
 196 Martinez et al., 2012; Rivera et al., 2011). Based on work done in insects (Arthropoda) and
 197 *Caenorhabditis elegans* (Nematoda), there are at least two pathways for long dsRNA to enter
 198 cells. **Clathrin-dependent endocytosis** encapsulates dsRNA in intracellular vesicles, followed

199 by release of dsRNA into the cytosol via endosomal escape (Zhu and Palli, 2020), as observed in
200 several insect orders: Coleoptera (Cappelle et al., 2016), Orthoptera (Wynant et al., 2014),
201 Diptera (Abbasi et al., 2020), and Hemiptera (Ye et al., 2021). *C. elegans* have a class of
202 transmembrane proteins collectively known as **SID proteins** (systemic RNA interference
203 defective proteins) that allow dsRNA molecules to enter cells (*e.g.*, gut epithelial cells) via
204 facilitated passive transport (Feinberg and Hunter, 2003; Winston et al., 2002). It is not known
205 how common this mechanism of dsRNA uptake is across invertebrates, as only two orthologs
206 (SID 1 and 3) of the four known families of SID proteins have been found in insects (Cappelle et
207 al., 2016; Vélez and Fishilevich, 2018; Xu and Han, 2008). Overall, the efficacy of dsRNA
208 uptake into cells can vary substantially among species and cell types (Zhu and Palli, 2020).

209

210 *3.2 dsRNA processing in the cytosol*

211 For the RNAi process to suppress gene expression, dsRNA must be processed by a variety of
212 proteins within a cell (Figure 2). Once long dsRNA enters the cytosol, **Dicer** (an
213 endoribonuclease) cleaves these molecules into smaller (19-25 bp) **siRNAs** (short interfering
214 RNAs; MacRae et al., 2006). These siRNAs are then recognized and loaded onto **Argonaute**
215 proteins, which facilitate the degradation of one strand of the siRNA to generate single-stranded
216 guide siRNA (Hutvagner and Simard, 2008). Together, this guide siRNA, Argonaute proteins
217 and Dicer form **RISC** (RNA-induced silencing complex; Martinez and Tuschl, 2004). RISC
218 binds to and then degrades mRNA with a sequence complementary to the guide siRNA
219 (Martinez and Tuschl, 2004). In some situations when there is incomplete sequence
220 complementary, siRNAs and the RISC complex can repress translation without fully degrading
221 the mRNA transcript (Zeng et al., 2003). The target mRNA transcript can no longer be translated

222 into a functional protein, leading to a knockdown of gene expression (Wilson and Doudna,
223 2013). While the introduction of dsRNA into all animal cells will elicit some form of RISC-
224 dependent RNAi response, the efficacy of dsRNA processing can still vary among species and
225 cell types and based on the properties of the dsRNA construct itself (*e.g.*, % sequence
226 complementarity; Zeng et al., 2003).

227

228 *3.3 Systemic RNAi and cell-to-cell communication*

229 The effect of RNAi is systemic in some species, resulting in suppression of gene expression in
230 multiple tissue types (Scott et al., 2013). This can occur via effective uptake of dsRNA from the
231 extracellular environment by many cells, but there is also evidence that RNAi can proceed via
232 cell-to-cell transport of dsRNA or siRNA (Figure 2). For example, SID proteins facilitate
233 intercellular dsRNA transport in *C. elegans* (Hinas et al., 2012). Nanotubes observed in *D.*
234 *melanogaster* could also potentially facilitate dsRNA transport among similar cell types
235 (Karlikow et al., 2016). In addition, exosome-type vesicles present in the hemolymph
236 (circulatory fluid) of insects could efficiently transport long dsRNA to multiple tissues and cell
237 types, as seen in *D. melanogaster* (Tassetto et al., 2017) and *Leptinotarsa decemlineata* (Yoon et
238 al., 2018). In *C. elegans*, the RNAi response can be “amplified” by host cells through the use of
239 **RNA-dependent RNA polymerases (RdRp)** that synthesize secondary siRNAs (Sijen et al.,
240 2001; Y. Zhang et al., 2022). There is currently no evidence that insects possess any RdRps
241 despite evidence of systemic RNAi responses (Tomoyasu et al., 2008). Thus, the extent to which
242 RNAi responses are systemic, and the mechanisms which drive cell-to-cell communication of
243 RNAi signals, may vary considerably among taxa.

244

245 **4 When and why a physiologist should choose RNAi**

246 *4.1 Temporary and partial knockdown is a feature, not a bug*

247 In the age of CRISPR and other novel genetic tools, why use the comparatively older technique
248 of RNAi? RNAi has several benefits, including its ability to produce temporary and partial
249 knockdowns. If the researcher is interested in studying phenotypes that occur under specific
250 environmental conditions or at specific times in an organism's life history, the ability to knock
251 down gene function in a narrow time frame can be more informative than permanently knocking
252 out a gene (see *Section 5*). In addition, if fully knocking out a gene would result in the animal's
253 death prior to the physiological state of interest, the ability to instead knock down a gene
254 temporarily (for a few days), and often partially (reduce but not eliminate the protein) using
255 RNAi (or other knockdown method) is attractive. For example, knocking out or strongly
256 knocking down the cytoskeletal protein beta-actin is lethal in many animals (*e.g.*, Dunn et al.,
257 2007; He et al., 2020; Tondeleir et al., 2014). However, nonlethal and partial knockdown of beta-
258 actin via RNAi is possible in several species (Dunn et al., 2007; Rivera et al., 2011), permitting
259 knockdown studies of processes that involve this gene. In addition, RNAi makes it fairly easy to
260 knock down multiple genes at a time (*e.g.*, by injecting/feeding dsRNA for multiple target
261 mRNAs; Cappelle et al., 2016; Giesbrecht et al., 2020; Miller et al., 2012; Tröbe et al., 2015),
262 which may be useful to manipulate multiple processes or pathways at once.

264 *4.2 Practical considerations*

265 RNAi may also be the only feasible option for genetic manipulation in some non-model
266 organisms. For example, it is difficult (or impossible) to generate and maintain genetic knockout
267 lines (Matthews and Vosshall, 2020) in animals that have long generation times (*e.g.*, annual life

268 cycles) or cannot be effectively reared in laboratories (*e.g.*, many freeze-tolerant insects;
269 Toxopeus and Sinclair, 2018). Even when the creation of genetic lines is feasible, maintenance
270 of those lines can be resource intensive, which may be less feasible in certain types of
271 institutions (*e.g.*, primarily undergraduate universities/colleges) or geographic regions. Thus, in
272 many instances RNAi will be the more practical choice for researchers, especially when working
273 with a target for which a pharmacological inhibitor does not exist.

275 **5 How to design and execute effective RNAi experiments in physiology**

276 *5.1 Flipping the paradigm: focusing on physiological phenotypes, not genes*

277 RNAi studies that characterize gene function can be important preliminary steps to making the
278 link between gene function and physiology, but how do we extract useful information about
279 physiology itself using RNAi? If the researcher is gene-focused, RNAi can be used to
280 characterize the function of novel genes (*e.g.*, King and MacRae, 2012; Sim and Denlinger,
281 2011) or validate whether a gene with known function in model organisms has that same
282 function in a specific non-model organism (*e.g.*, Smith et al., 2012; Toxopeus et al., 2014; Xie et
283 al., 2019b). However, in cases where RNAi produces conflicting results (*e.g.*, compare Colinet et
284 al., 2010; Udaka et al., 2013), genetic knockouts may provide more conclusive answers (*e.g.*,
285 Newman et al., 2017). We therefore agree with others (Boettcher and McManus, 2015; Schulte-
286 Merker and Stainier, 2014; Zimmer et al., 2019) that genetic knockouts remain a gold standard
287 for assessing gene function.

288

289 If the researcher is physiology-focused, we must move beyond the characterization of gene
290 function. For example, if we know that a cellular or molecular pathway relies on a particular

291 gene, RNAi of that gene can be used to understand the function of that pathway in a
292 physiological process and how it produces an organismal phenotype (Figure 3). Lebenzon et al.,
293 (2022) used this approach to test whether mitophagy (a cellular pathway) drove decreased
294 metabolic rates (organismal phenotype) in dormant Colorado potato beetles *L. decemlineata* by
295 knocking down a gene (*Parkin*) that was essential for the mitophagy process. Conversely, if the
296 pathway/process underlying a phenotype is not well known, RNAi can be used to better
297 understand the pathway/process. For example, a series of RNAi experiments have been used to
298 understand how insulin signalling regulates photoperiodic induction of insect dormancy
299 (diapause; *e.g.*, Mano and Goto, 2022; Sim and Denlinger, 2008, 2009). In both examples above,
300 the gene is a convenient tool for the physiologist to manipulate a process, rather than the gene
301 being the focus of the study. We will focus the remainder of this section on how to design useful
302 experiments using the logic that knocking down a gene will allow physiologists to manipulate
303 processes to identify the relative contribution of that process to producing physiologically
304 interesting phenotypes (Figure 3).

305

307

308 **Figure 3. Experimental logic of using RNAi to explore connections between physiological**
 309 **processes and phenotypes.** Here we show how RNAi can be used to better understand how
 310 physiological processes drive certain phenotypes. By manipulating a target process *via* RNAi
 311 knockdown of a process-related gene, physiologists can begin to explore whether or not these
 312 gene-mediated processes are necessary for producing phenotypes of interest. Suggested actions
 313 are displayed in blue boxes, potential outcomes are displayed in yellow boxes, and potential
 314 conclusions are displayed in white boxes. Arrows indicate the direction of workflow. KD =
 315 knockdown.

316

317 5.2 Identifying a biologically relevant RNAi target

318 To identify an appropriate RNAi target, one must identify whether the target gene is upregulated
 319 in the organismal phenotype or process of interest (Figure 4). Increased expression of a target
 320 mRNA transcript indicates that more protein product is on its way, so RNAi could prevent the
 321 accumulation of that protein and ultimately prevent the process from occurring. To measure
 322 mRNA transcript abundance, both real time quantitative PCR (RT-qPCR; *e.g.* Chen et al., 2024)

323 transcriptomic (RNA-seq) datasets can be a useful (*e.g.*, Kaplanoglu et al., 2017). If the target
 324 gene is not upregulated in association with the phenotype or process of interest, then there is no *a*
 325 *priori* expectation that RNAi of the target will have an impact, and it's time to identify a new
 326 candidate mRNA transcript (Figure 4) or consider an alternative approach to inhibiting your
 327 target (*e.g.*, using pharmacological manipulation of protein activity).

328
 329 **Figure 4. A workflow for development of your RNAi protocol.** Suggested actions are in blue
 330 boxes, potential outcomes are displayed in yellow boxes, and the black boxes indicate the written
 331 section number with full workflow explanations. Arrows indicate the direction of workflow. KD
 332 = knockdown.
 333

334 *5.3 Developing and validating your RNAi protocol*

335 Once you have identified a target gene that will allow you to manipulate a process or phenotype
 336 of interest, you can design dsRNA constructs complementary to the target gene, optimize the

337 delivery of your construct(s) and validate the knockdown of your target *in vivo* (Figure 4).
338 Designing dsRNA constructs is the first step in ensuring successful gene knockdown. This might
339 sound like a daunting task for a physiologist-turned-molecular biologist, but is simple enough to
340 do using publicly-available dsRNA construct software (such as E-RNAi, <http://www.e-rnai.org/>)
341 based on the mRNA transcript sequence in your animal of interest (*i.e.*, from personal or publicly
342 available genomic/transcriptomic data sets). Because we focus this workflow on *non-model*
343 organisms, it is likely that researchers might not have access to publicly available mRNA
344 sequences, so researchers may have to initially design primers using mRNA sequences from
345 closely related species.

346

347 It is important to design or use an existing negative control construct to ensure that any effects of
348 your RNAi experiment are based on knockdown of the target gene rather than **off-target** effects
349 elicited by the introduction of exogenous dsRNA. Appropriate negative controls could include a
350 dsRNA construct with a scrambled sequence (*e.g.*, Mysore et al., 2019), or one complementary
351 to a sequence that the animal will never endogenously express (*e.g.*, most animals don't express
352 *green fluorescent protein*: Lebenzon et al., 2022; Toxopeus et al., 2014). You can then order or
353 synthesize the dsRNA constructs (using one of many commercially available kits, *e.g.*,
354 Thermofisher MEGAscript™ RNAi Kit) and deliver them into your animal (*e.g.*, by injecting,
355 feeding, soaking).

356

357 Before proceeding with measuring the impact of RNA on your process or phenotype of interest,
358 it is essential to test whether your RNAi protocol causes a biologically meaningful knockdown of
359 the target. This knockdown must be validated at the transcript level (*e.g.*, using RT-qPCR), and

360 ideally at the protein level (using immunoblotting, or an enzyme activity assay) where possible.
361 We define a “biologically-meaningful knockdown” as at least 50% knockdown of your target
362 transcript (but 70-90% knockdown is better) in a group of individuals exposed to dsRNA for
363 your target gene compared to a group of individuals exposed to the negative control dsRNA
364 construct. Typically, this comparison should be between at least six biological replicates per
365 group (*i.e.*, $n \geq 6$ negative control dsRNA, $n \geq 6$ target dsRNA) to have enough statistical power
366 to detect a difference. We also recommend verifying that the knockdown is repeatable either
367 with a higher sample size, or multiple rounds of knockdowns, each with at least six biological
368 replicates.

369
370 It is important to measure both the *extent* (% decrease in expression compared to your negative
371 control) and *timing* (how long it takes your gene to be knocked down) of gene knockdown,
372 because RNAi itself is a biological process that takes time. This can be accomplished by
373 sampling a subset of individuals at several time points past dsRNA delivery, to create a time-
374 course of gene knockdown, typically between 1 and 14 days post-dsRNA delivery (*e.g.*,
375 Meyering-Vos and Müller, 2007; Sim and Denlinger, 2011; Xie et al., 2019a) to detect when
376 mRNA abundance of the target is at a minimum. This involves some up-front cost in the form of
377 processing many animals before your downstream experiments even begin; gene expression data
378 must be collected from at least six individuals injected with each dsRNA construct (your
379 negative control or gene of interest), per time point to ensure enough statistical power to detect a
380 significant difference in gene expression. RNAi is temporary and typically knockdowns only last
381 days to weeks, but it is possible to observe some longer-term effects (*e.g.*, *HSP90* knockdown in
382 *Culex pipiens* larvae can persist into adulthood; Lopez-Martinez et al., 2012). Either way, it is

383 crucial to understand the timeline of your gene manipulation to ensure that your physiological
384 process/phenotype of interest is also congruent with the timing of knockdown (see *Section 5.5*).
385 If no significant (or relevant) knockdown is observed within a logical timeframe for your
386 proposed downstream experiments, further optimization of your knockdown protocol is required
387 (Figure 4).

388

389 *5.4 Optimizing your RNAi protocol*

390 There can be challenges at any point in the RNAi process (see *Section 3*) that prevent you from
391 observing a biologically relevant gene knockdown, including dsRNA uptake, dsRNA processing,
392 efficacy of systemic RNAi. Some of these challenges are difficult to overcome in species that are
393 recalcitrant to RNAi. For example, spiny lobsters (*Panulirus ornatus*) have low RNAi efficacy
394 and expression of *Dicer* and *Argonaute* compared to their close (and amenable-to-RNAi)
395 relative, slipper lobsters (*Thenus australiensis*; Banks et al., 2022, 2020). However, other
396 challenges can be overcome by modifying your RNAi protocol. In this section, we provide some
397 practical advice on how the RNAi protocol can be modified to address these challenges and
398 optimize your gene knockdowns. Of course, with each change to your protocol, it is important to
399 follow-up with validation (*Section 5.3*; Figure 4).

400

401 dsRNA length and sequence may influence the efficacy of the RNAi response, so dsRNA
402 construct choice is an important part of protocol optimization. For example, in *C. elegans* and
403 many insects, short dsRNAs (<40 bps) are not effectively taken up by cells (e.g., Clemens et al.,
404 2000; Miller et al., 2012), so designing long dsRNA constructs (e.g., 200-500 bp) is important
405 for ensuring a strong and stable knockdown. In addition, in some species dsRNA processing (i.e.,

406 cleavage into siRNAs, see *Section 3.2*) is affected by the dsRNA sequence itself (Fan et al.,
407 2022). It is therefore often useful to design and test a variety of constructs for a single target gene
408 (*e.g.*, He et al., 2020). In some cases, it may be possible to skip the dsRNA processing entirely
409 by exposing animals directly to siRNAs. For example, a taxonomically diverse group of
410 invertebrates are amenable to RNAi via injection of siRNAs (< 25 bp) - including honeybees
411 (Arthropoda; Guo et al., 2018; Y. Zhang et al., 2022), earthworms (Annelida; Paul et al., 2022),
412 sea cucumbers (Echinodermata; Li et al., 2020), razor clams (Mollusca; Li et al., 2021), and
413 hydras (Cnidaria; Suknovic et al., 2021). Again, the impact of siRNAs can be sequence specific
414 (*e.g.*, Suknovic et al., 2021). Therefore, if longer dsRNA molecules are not working, testing a
415 suite of siRNAs may be a good alternative.

416
417 Another important aspect of knockdown optimization is considering how your dsRNA delivery
418 impacts RNAi efficacy. Some animals are recalcitrant to RNAi because nucleases in the
419 gastrointestinal tract or hemolymph degrade dsRNA molecules before they can ever enter cells
420 (*e.g.*, Christiaens et al., 2014; Guan et al., 2018; Hoang et al., 2022; Luo et al., 2013). For species
421 with high gut nuclease activity (*e.g.*, locusts; Luo et al., 2013), it is better to use injection rather
422 than feeding as a delivery method, or use feeding in combination with inhibitors of those RNA
423 nucleases (*e.g.*, Giesbrecht et al., 2020). Some species have naturally low uptake of (intact)
424 dsRNA or siRNAs into cells. For example, *D. melanogaster* exhibits limited knockdown in most
425 tissue types (*i.e.*, RNAi is not systemic) if dsRNA is administered via injection (*e.g.*, Miller et al.,
426 2008), leading most researchers to instead use transgenic RNAi lines in this species (*e.g.*, Freda
427 et al., 2022). In non-model organisms with low dsRNA uptake, a delivery vehicle or modified
428 delivery technique may improve uptake, *e.g.*, encapsulation of the nucleic acids into liposomes

429 (Adams et al., 2019; Lin et al., 2017; Snell et al., 2011), nanoparticles (Dhandapani et al., 2019;
430 Lu et al., 2022; X. Zhang et al., 2022), or viruses (Gu et al., 2011). In some animals (mostly
431 aquatic species), electroporation is also an option to improve dsRNA uptake (Alicea-Delgado
432 and García-Arrarás, 2021; Correnti et al., 2005; Masuda-Ozawa et al., 2022; Okude et al., 2017).
433 Further, RNAi is often dose-dependent (*e.g.*, Miller et al., 2012; Priya et al., 2010), so it is
434 usually advisable to conduct a pilot study that compares administration of different
435 concentrations of dsRNA or siRNAs. It may be worth trying a variety of dsRNA delivery
436 methods and concentrations before giving up hope!

437

438 One consideration that may be especially relevant to invertebrate physiologists is the potential
439 impact of environmental or experimental conditions on RNAi itself, especially in the context of
440 stress physiology or ecophysiology. For example, low temperature can inhibit RNAi efficacy
441 (*e.g.*, Fortier and Belote, 2000; Kameda et al., 2004), likely because temperature can potentially
442 affect many mechanisms involved in RNAi (Figure 2). Low temperatures decrease membrane
443 fluidity and rates of endocytosis (Rode et al., 1997; Wolkers et al., 2003), which could decrease
444 dsRNA uptake by cells. Even when organisms are genetically modified to produce dsRNA
445 within cells, siRNA production can be reduced at low temperatures (*e.g.*, in tobacco; Szittyta et
446 al., 2003), perhaps because low temperatures can inhibit enzyme activity (*e.g.*, Dicer). If siRNA
447 production is normal at low temperatures, RNAi may still be inhibited (*e.g.*, in mosquitos;
448 Adelman et al., 2013), suggesting that a mechanism downstream of Dicer is temperature
449 sensitive, such as RISC formation or siRNA base-pairing with target mRNA. Expression of core
450 RNA machinery can also be downregulated when organisms are exposed to low temperature,
451 *e.g.*, Dicer and Argonaute in the fruit fly *Bactrocera dorsalis* (Xie et al., 2017). However, some

452 organisms have perfectly functional RNAi in the face of low temperatures (Košťál and
453 Tollarová-Borovanská, 2009; Vatanparast et al., 2022; Romon et al., 2013), so the impact of
454 temperature on RNAi likely depends on the species and the environment it is adapted or
455 acclimatized to.

456

457 *5.5 Testing physiologically relevant hypotheses with RNAi*

458 Once you have developed and optimized your RNAi protocol, the fun (hypothesis testing!) can
459 begin. We will walk through the experimental design and logic that can be used to answer the
460 Questions we identified earlier (Figure 1) and note that many other ecophysiological questions
461 could be tested using RNAi and similar logic. At a basic level, the experimental design must still
462 include at least two groups: individuals exposed to dsRNA for the target mRNA (knockdown)
463 and individuals exposed to negative control dsRNA (no knockdown), all under the same protocol
464 that was appropriately optimized validated in prior steps (*Sections 5.3, 5.4*). At a more nuanced
465 level, the physiologist has some careful choices to make concerning the timing of RNAi, because
466 *when* a process is manipulated can certainly impact the resulting phenotype and interpretation of
467 the results (Figure 5).

468

469 For Question 1, the timing of gene knockdowns will differ depending on whether your
470 hypothesis focuses on a process involved in the *regulation* of a phenotype or the *downstream*
471 *mechanisms* linked to that phenotype (Figure 5, Q1). For example, to determine the role of
472 insulin signaling (the process of interest) in the regulation of diapause (the organismal phenotype
473 of interest) in the mosquito *C. pipiens*, Sim and Denlinger (2008) knocked down an insulin
474 receptor to manipulate insulin signaling *before entry* into diapause. In the same study, the authors

475 explored the mechanisms underlying lipid accumulation (a process linked to the phenotype of
476 diapause) by knocking down forkhead box-O transcription factor *during* diapause (Sim and
477 Denlinger, 2008). By using different timing of knockdowns, the authors were able to disentangle
478 the processes involved in diapause regulation and downstream fat storage during diapause itself.

479
480 For Question 2, we focus on a challenging environmental condition, and in this case the timing
481 of knockdowns depends on whether the hypothesis is focused on *survival* of (resistance to) the
482 challenge or *recovery* from the challenge (Figure 5, Q2). For example, consider the impact of the
483 chaperone response (process of interest) on insect cold tolerance. To determine whether heat
484 shock proteins (a type of chaperone) were important for survival of sub-zero temperatures in the
485 flesh fly, *Sarcophaga crassipalpis*, Rinehart et al. (2007) knocked them down *before* cold
486 exposure and found that this impaired immediate survival. Conversely, to measure the impact of
487 chaperone knockdown on recovery from cold stress in the red linden bug, *Pyrrhocoris apterus*,
488 Košťál and Tollarová-Borovanská (2009) knocked the heat shock protein gene down *after*
489 exposure to low temperatures. Timing of RNAi can therefore have a strong impact on the types
490 (and utility) of conclusions one can draw.

491
492 The ultimate goal of answering our proposed research questions is to understand the relative
493 importance of certain processes on physiological phenotypes, which should include phenotypes
494 at multiple levels of biological organization. Thus, researchers should strive to assess how RNAi
495 affects organismal phenotypes of interest but also any associated cellular and tissue-level
496 phenotypes (Figure 5). For example, to determine the role of flight muscle mitophagy (a form of
497 mitochondrial-specific autophagy, the process of interest) in driving low metabolic rates during

498 diapause (the rare phenotype), Lebenzon et al. (2022) used RNAi to knock down a mitophagy-
 499 related gene. The authors assessed how the RNAi knockdown impacted organismal level
 500 metabolic rates, but also assessed RNAi impacts on cell ultrastructure, enzyme activity and
 501 mitochondrial function (Lebenzon et al., 2022). This approach facilitates making stronger
 502 mechanistic links between genotype and understandings of physiological phenotype.

503
 504 **Figure 5. Physiologically relevant hypothesis testing using your successful RNAi toolkit.** We
 505 present two putative questions that physiologists might want to answer using RNAi, and the
 506 associated workflow and logic to be used to answer those questions. Hypotheses related to “Q1”
 507 are displayed in purple boxes, hypotheses related to “Q2” are displayed in orange boxes, and
 508 suggested experimental actions are in blue boxes. Arrows indicate the suggested workflow. KD
 509 = knockdown.
 510

511 **6 Conclusions**

512 Genetic manipulation as a tool for biological exploration has been around for decades, with tools
513 becoming more accessible (both technically and financially) in the last two decades with the
514 discovery of RNAi. For ecophysiologicalists to continue expanding our knowledge at multiple levels
515 of biological organization, it is important to take advantage of these tools in well-designed
516 experiments. Thus, we hope that more researchers will use RNAi in a meaningful way to bridge
517 the gap between physiological phenotype and genotype to further our mechanistic understanding
518 of invertebrate ecophysiology.

PRE-PROOF

519 **Glossary**

520 Argonaute: proteins that facilitate formation of RISC and conversion of double-stranded siRNA

521 to single-stranded guide siRNA in the RNAi process

522 Clathrin-dependent endocytosis: invagination of the cell's plasma membrane to generate

523 clathrin-coated vesicles, usually in response to activation of a transmembrane receptor

524 CRISPR: tool that can be used to modify (edit) DNA sequences complementary to a short DNA

525 sequence in combination with Cas (CRISPR-associated) proteins

526 Dicer: enzyme that cleaves long dsRNA into siRNAs

527 Downstream: refers to a process that occurs after some other process of interest

528 Endogenous: originating from within an organism, *e.g.*, microRNAs produced within a cell

529 Exogenous: originating from outside of an organism, *e.g.*, dsRNA from a viral infection

530 Gain-of-function experiment: the impact of increased expression of the target gene is studied

531 Genotype: genetic sequence(s) in an organism

532 Knockdown (noun) or knock down (verb): genetic manipulation used in a loss-of-function

533 experiment to partially expression of a target gene

534 Knock-in (noun), or knock in (verb): genetic manipulation used in a gain-of-function experiment

535 to increase expression of a target gene

536 Knockout (noun), or knock out (verb): genetic manipulation used in a loss-of-function

537 experiment to eliminate expression of a functional gene product

538 Loss-of-function experiment: the impact of decreased in expression of the target gene is studied

539 Morpholino: tool that prevents translation of target mRNA via cellular exposure to a modified

540 DNA oligomer complementary to target mRNA

541 Off-target effects: refers to an impact of an experimental manipulation on an organism's
542 genotype or phenotype that was not intended (affected something other than the 'target')

543 Pharmacological inhibitor: chemical (drug) that inhibits the function of a target protein

544 Phenotype: the traits of an organism at any level of biological organization, based fully or
545 partially on expression of genetic sequences

546 RdRp: RNA polymerases that can synthesize RNA using other RNA as a template

547 RISC: complex of Argonaute proteins, Dicer, and guide siRNA that binds to and degrades target
548 mRNA during the RNAi process

549 RNAi: process that causes degradation of target mRNA via cellular exposure to dsRNA or
550 siRNA complementary to target mRNA

551 SID proteins: a group of transmembrane proteins that facilitate transport of dsRNA into cells in
552 some organisms

553 siRNA: short (19-25 bp) RNA molecules that guide RISC to degrade complementary mRNA in
554 the RNAi process

555 TALEN: nucleases that can be used to modify (edit) DNA by causing targeted double-stranded
556 breaks that are incorrectly repaired by the cell

557 Target: used in genetics to refer to the gene or protein of interest, *e.g.*, target for knockdown

558 Targeted transformation: any genetic method that is used to selectively modify (mutate, edit) a
559 genetic sequence in an organism

560 Transgenic: adjective for an organism whose genetic material has been permanently modified

561 Untargeted mutagenesis: use of a method that indiscriminately mutates DNA (*e.g.*, exposure to
562 ionizing radiation) to (usually) generate genetic knockouts

563

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569

570 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

571 None. The authors have no competing interests to declare.

572

573

PRE-PRINT

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